

$\alpha\beta$ and $s\beta$ -closed functions in Topology *

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Abstract

Aim of this paper is to study the properties of $s\beta$ - regular spaces and $s\beta$ - closed functions, using β -open (semipreopen sets) sets and semiclosed sets.

1 Introduction

In the literature semiopen sets plays an vital in general topology, due to Normal Levine [11]. In 1965, O. Njastad [21] introduced the concept of α - sets and properties of α - open sets was introduced by A.S. Mashhour et al. [15] the paper contains the notions of α - continuous functions, α - open functions and α - closed functions. In 1983 , the concepts of β - open sets, β - closed sets , β - continuous functions , β - open functions and β - closed functions were introduced and studied by M.E.Abd El-Monsef et al. [1] . D.Andrijevic [4] introduced semipreopen sets and semipreclosed sets respectively and obtained their properties. Later in 1995 Park et al [23] introduced sp-regular spaces. In this paper we define and study the properties of $\alpha\beta$ - closed functions , $s\beta$ - closed functions, $s\beta$ - regular spaces, composition mappings and results on space preservation.

2 Preliminaries

Throughout the paper (X, τ) , (Y, σ) and (Z, γ) (or simply, X, Y and Z) denote topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. If A is any subset of X, then $\text{Cl}(A)$ and $\text{Int}(A)$ denote the closure and the interior of A respectively.

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DEFINITION 1 A subset A of X is said to be

- (i) semiopen[11] if $A \subset ClInt(A)$
- (ii) α -open[21] if $A \subset IntCl(Int(A))$
- (iii) semipreopen[4] if $A \subset Cl(IntCl(A))$
- (iv) $g\beta$ - closed (= gsp-closed) [9]
if $\beta Cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is open in X

The complement of a semiopen (resp. α -open, semipreopen (α -open)) set of X is called a semiclosed (resp. α -closed, semipreclosed (α -closed)) set in X and the complement of a $g\beta$ -closed set is called $g\beta$ -open set in X . The family of all semiopen (resp. α -open, β -open) sets of X is denoted by $SO(X)$ (resp. $\alpha O(X)$, $\beta O(X)$) and that of semiclosed (resp. α -closed, β -closed) sets of X is denoted by $SF(X)$ (resp. $\alpha F(X)$), $\beta F(X)$).

DEFINITION 2 [5, 4, 2] Let A be a subset of a space X , then

- (i) The intersection of all semi-closed sets containing A is called semi-closure of A and is denoted by $sCl(A)$
- (ii) The intersection of all semipreclosed sets containing A is called semipre-closure of A or β -closure of A and is denoted by $spCl(A)$ or $\beta Cl(A)$

DEFINITION 3 [5, 4, 2] Let A be a subset of a space X , then

- (i) The semi - interior of A is defined by the union of all semieopen sets contained in A and is denoted by $sInt(A)$.
- (ii) The semipre - interior of A is defined by the union of all semipreopen sets contained in A and is denoted by $spInt(A)$

DEFINITION 4 A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called

- (i) semicontinuous [11] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is semiopen in X for every open set V of Y
- (ii) semiprecontinuous [16] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is semiopen in X for every open set V of Y
- (iii) irresolute [6] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is semiopen in X for every semiopen set V of Y .
- (iv) β -irresolute [13] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is β -open in X for every β -open set V of Y .
- (v) α -irresolute [12] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is α -open in X for every α -open set V of Y .
- (vi) β -continuous [1] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is β -open in X for every open set V of Y

DEFINITION 5 A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called

- (i) *semiclosed* [22] if $f(F)$ is *semiclosed set* in Y for each *closed set* F of X .
- (ii) *presemiclosed* [10] if $f(F)$ is *semiclosed set* in Y for each *semiclosed set* F of X .
- (iii) *pre - α -open* [7] if $f(U)$ is *α - open set* in Y for each *α -open set* U of X .
- (iv) *pre - α -closed* [7] if $f(U)$ is *α - closed set* in Y for each *α -closed set* U of X .
- (v) *pre - β -open* [13] if $f(U)$ is *β - open set* in Y for each *β -open set* U of X .
- (vi) *pre - β -closed* [13] if $f(U)$ is *β - closed set* in Y for each *β -closed set* U of X .
- (vii) *presemiopen* [6] if $f(U)$ is *semiopen set* in Y for each *semiopen set* U of X .
- (viii) *β -closed* [1] if $f(F)$ is *β -closed set* in Y for each *closed set* F of X .
- (ix) *α -closed* [15] if $f(F)$ is *α -closed set* in Y for each *closed set* F of X .
- (x) *$\alpha g\beta$ - closed* [20] if $f(F)$ is *$g\beta$ - closed set* in Y for each *α -closed set* F of X .

DEFINITION 6 A topological space (X, τ) is said to be

- (i) *β - regular* [3] provided that every *closed set* F and a *point* x not in F , can be separated by *disjoint β - open sets*.
- (ii) *semiregular* [8] provided that every *semiclosed set* F and a *point* x not in F , can be separated by *disjoint semiopen sets*.
- (iii) *$\alpha\beta$ -regular* [18] provided that every *α - closed set* F and a *point* x not in F , can be separated by *disjoint β -open sets*.
- (iv) *β - normal* [13] provided that every pair of *non-empty disjoint closed sets* can be separated by *disjoint β - open sets*.
- (v) *$\alpha\beta$ - normal* [18] provided that every pair of *non-empty disjoint α -closed sets* can be separated by *disjoint β - open sets*.
- (vi) *αT_1 -space* [14] if for any *distinct pair of points* x and y in X , there is an *α -open set* U in X containing x but not y and an *open set* V in X containing y but not x resp., with $U \cap V \neq \emptyset$.

3 $\alpha\beta$ - closed functions

DEFINITION 7 A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be $\alpha\beta$ -closed if the image of each α -closed set of X is β -closed in Y .

EXAMPLE 3.1 Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$ and $Y = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$, $\sigma = \{\emptyset, \{1\}, \{2, 3\}, \{1, 2, 3\}, Y\}$. Define $f : X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(a) = 1, f(b) = 2, f(c) = 3, f(d) = f(e) = 5$ clearly, f is $\alpha\beta$ -closed function.

THEOREM 3.2 A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed if and only if any subset A of Y and any α -open set F containing $f^{-1}(A)$, there is a β -open set G of Y containing A such that $f^{-1}(G) \subset F$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed function and $A \subset Y$ and F is α -open set of X containing $f^{-1}(A)$. Put $G = Y - f(X - F)$. Then G is β -open set of Y , $A \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(G) \subset F$

Sufficiency. Let K be any α -closed set of X . Put $B = Y - f(K)$ then $f^{-1}(B) \subset X \setminus K$ and $X - K$ is α -open in X . There exists a β -open set G of Y such that $B = Y - f(K) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(G) \subset X - K$

Therefore $f(K) = Y - G$ and hence $f(K)$ is β -closed in Y

Some results on $\alpha\beta$ - closed functions and allied mappings :

THEOREM 3.3 If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ be two functions such that $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed function:

- (i) If f is α -irresolute surjection then g is $\alpha\beta$ -closed
- (ii) If g is β -irresolute injection then f is $\alpha\beta$ -closed

Proof. (i) Let U be an arbitrary α -closed set in Y . Since $g \circ f$ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed and f is α -irresolute and surjective then $g(U) = g \circ f(f^{-1}(U))$ is a β -closed set in Z . Hence, g is $\alpha\beta$ -closed.

(ii) Since g is injective, we remark that $f(A) = g^{-1}(g(f(A)))$ for every subset A of X . Let U be an arbitrary α -closed set in X , then by hypothesis $(g \circ f)(U)$ is a β - closed set in Z . Again $f(U) = g^{-1}(g \circ f)(U)$ is β - closed in Y . Since g is β -irresolute and injective. This shows $f(U)$ is β - closed in Y . Hence, f is $\alpha\beta$ - closed

THEOREM 3.4 : *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is pre - α -closed and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ is $\alpha\beta$ closed then $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed*

Proof. Let U be an arbitrary α -closed set in X . Since f is pre- α -closed, $f(U)$ is α -closed in Y . Again, since g is $\alpha\beta$ closed and $f(U)$ is α -closed, $g(f(U)) = (g \circ f)(U)$ is β -closed in Z . This shows $g \circ f$ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed.

DEFINITION 8 *A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be quasi- α - closed function if the image of each α -closed set of X is closed in Y .*

EXAMPLE 3.5 *Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$ and $Y = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $\sigma = \{\emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2\}, \{2, 3\}, Y\}$. Define $f : X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(a) = 1, f(b) = f(c) = 2, f(d) = f(e) = 3$. Then f is quasi- α -closed function.*

THEOREM 3.6 : *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is quasi - α - closed and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ is β - closed then $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is $\alpha\beta$ - closed*

Proof. straight forward.

4 $s\beta$ - closed functions

DEFINITION 9 *A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be $s\beta$ - closed function if the image of each semiclosed set of X is β -closed in Y .*

EXAMPLE 4.1 *Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$ and $Y = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$, $\sigma = \{\emptyset, \{1\}, \{2, 3\}, \{1, 2, 3\}, Y\}$ Define $f : X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(a) = 1, f(b) = f(c) = 2, f(d) = f(e) = 4$. clearly, f is $s\beta$ -closed function.*

THEOREM 4.2 *A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $s\beta$ -closed if and only if any subset A of Y and any α -open set F of X containing $f^{-1}(A)$, there is a β -open set G of Y containing A such that $f^{-1}(G) \subset F$.*

Proof. Is similar to Theorem 3.2

THEOREM 4.3 *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ be two functions such that $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is $s\beta$ -closed function:*

- (i) *If f is irresolute surjection then g is $s\beta$ -closed*
- (ii) *If g is β -irresolute injection then f is $s\beta$ -closed*

Proof. Is similar to Theorem 3.3

THEOREM 4.4 : *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is presemiclosed and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ is $s\beta$ -closed then $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is $s\beta$ -closed*

Proof. straight forward.

DEFINITION 10 *A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be quasi-semiclosed function if the image of each semiclosed set of X is closed in Y .*

EXAMPLE 4.5 *Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$ and $Y = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $\sigma = \{\emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1, 2\}, \{2, 3\}, Y\}$. Define $f : X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(a) = 1$, $f(b) = f(c) = 2$, $f(d) = f(e) = 3$. Then f is quasi-semiclosed function.*

THEOREM 4.6 : *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is quasi - semiclosed and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ is β - closed then $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is $s\beta$ - closed*

Proof. straight forward.

REMARK 4.7 : The functions defined above have following implications :

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 \text{pre-}\beta \text{ - closed} & \implies & \beta \text{ - closed} & & \\
 \downarrow & & \uparrow & & \\
 \uparrow \longrightarrow \text{s}\beta \text{ - closed} & \implies & \alpha\beta \text{ - closed} & \longleftarrow \uparrow & \\
 \uparrow & \uparrow & \uparrow & \uparrow & \\
 \uparrow \text{ quasi - semiclosed} & \implies & \text{quasi - } \alpha \text{ - closed} & \uparrow & \\
 \uparrow & \downarrow & \downarrow & \uparrow & \\
 \uparrow \longleftarrow \text{presemiclosed} & \longleftarrow & \text{pre - } \alpha \text{ - closed} & \longrightarrow \uparrow & \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \\
 \text{semiclosed} & \longleftarrow & \alpha \text{ - closed} & &
 \end{array}$$

None of the implications in the above are reversible.

EXAMPLE 4.8 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\sigma = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, Y\}$. Define $f : X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(a) = d, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$, Then f is pre- α -closed but not quasi-semiclosed.

EXAMPLE 4.9 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$ $Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\sigma = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, Y\}$. Define $f : X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(a) = d, f(b) = b, f(c) = d$, Then f is quasi-semiclosed and pre- β -closed

5 $s\beta$ - regular spaces

DEFINITION 11 A topological space (X, τ) is said to be $s\beta$ - regular for each semiclosed set F and a point x in $X - F$, there exist disjoint β - open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $F \subset V$

EXAMPLE 5.1 Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$, the space (X, τ) is $s\beta$ -regular but not semiregular.

REMARK 5.2 : The following implications hold in general :

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 s\beta - \text{regular space} & \implies & \alpha\beta - \text{regular} \\
 \uparrow & & \downarrow \\
 \text{semiregular space} & & \beta - \text{regular space}
 \end{array}$$

None of the implications in the above are reversible.

THEOREM 5.3 For the topological space (X) the following statements are equivalent :

- (i) X is $s\beta$ -regular
- (ii) For each $x \in X$ and for each semiopen set U containing x there exists a β -open set V containing x such that $x \in V \subset \beta Cl(V) \subset U$
- (iii) For each semiclosed set F of X , $\cap \{ \beta Cl(V) / F \subset V \in \beta O(X) \} = F$
- (iv) For each nonempty subset A of X and each $U \in SO(X)$ if $A \cap U \neq \emptyset$ then there exists $V \in \beta O(X)$ such that $A \cap V \neq \emptyset$ and $\beta Cl(V) \subset U$
- (v) For each nonempty subset A of X and each $F \in SF(X)$ if $A \cap F = \emptyset$ then there exists disjoint β - open sets V, W such that $A \cap V \neq \emptyset$ and $F \subset W$

Proof. (i) \rightarrow (ii) : Let X is $s\beta$ -regular space. Let $x \in X$ and U be semiopen set containing x implies $X - U$ is semiclosed such that $x \notin X - U$. Therefore by (i) there exists β open sets V and W such that $x \in V$ and $X - U \subset W$ which implies $X - W \subset U$. Since V and W disjoint $\beta Cl(V) \cap W = \emptyset$ results $\beta Cl(V) \subset X - W \subset U$. Therefore $x \in V \subset \beta Cl(V) \subset U$.

(ii) \rightarrow (iii) : Let F be a semiclosed subset of X and $x \notin F$. then $X - F$ is semiopen set containing x . By (ii) there exists β -open set U such that $x \in U \subset \beta Cl(U) \subset X - F$ implies $F \subset X - \beta Cl(U) \subset X - U$. which means $F \subset V \subset X - U$ where $V = X - \beta Cl(U) \in \beta O(X)$ and $x \notin V$ that implies $x \notin \beta Cl(V)$ $x \notin \cap \{ \beta Cl(V) / F \subset V \in \beta O(X) \}$. Therefore $\cap \{ \beta Cl(V) / F \subset V \in \beta O(X) \} = F$

(iii) \rightarrow (iv) : A be a subset of X and $U \in SO(X)$ such that $A \cap U \neq \emptyset$ there exist $x_0 \in X$ such that $x_0 \in A \cap U$ Therefore $X - U$ is semiclosed set not containing x_0 implies $x_0 \notin sCl(X - U)$. By (iii) there exists $W \in \beta O(X)$ such that $X - U \subset W$ results $x_0 \notin \beta Cl(W)$.

Put $V = X - \beta Cl(W)$, then V is β open set containing x_0 which implies $A \cap V \neq \emptyset$ and $\beta Cl(V) \subset \beta Cl(X - \beta Cl(W)) \subset \beta Cl(X - W)$. Therefore $\beta Cl(V) \subset \beta Cl(X - W) \subset U$.

(iv) \rightarrow (v) : Let A be a nonempty subset of X and F be semiclosed set such that $A \cap F = \emptyset$. Then $X - F$ is semiopen in X and $A \cap (X - F) \neq \emptyset$ Therefore by (iv), there exist $V \in \beta O(X)$ such that $A \cap V \neq \emptyset$ and $\beta Cl(V) \subset X - F$. Put $W = X - \beta Cl(V)$ then $W \in \beta O(X)$ such that $F \subset W$ and $W \cap V = \emptyset$.

(v) \rightarrow (i) : Let $x \in X$ be arbitrary and F be semiclosed set not containing x . Let $A = X - F$ be a nonempty semiopen set containing x then by (v) there exist disjoint β open sets V and W such that $F \subset W$ and $A \cap V \neq \emptyset$ implies $x \in V$. Thus X is β - regular.

Some space preservation results in the following :

THEOREM 5.4 *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a pre - β -open , irresolute bijection and X is $s\beta$ -regular space , then Y is $s\beta$ -regular.*

Proof. : Let F be any semiclosed subset of Y and $y \in Y$ with $y \notin F$. Since f is irresolute, $f^{-1}(F)$ is semiclosed set in X . Again, f is bijective, let $f(x) = y$, then $x \notin f^{-1}(F)$. Since X is $s\beta$ - regular , there exist disjoint β -open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $f^{-1}(F) \subset V$. Since f is , pre - β -open bijection, we have $y \in f(U)$ and $F \subset f(V)$ and $f(U) \cap f(V) = f(U \cap V) = \emptyset$ Hence, Y is $s\beta$ -regular.

THEOREM 5.5 *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is pre -semiclosed , β -irresolute injection and Y is $s\beta$ -regular space, then X is $s\beta$ -regular .*

Proof. : Let F be any semiclosed set of X and $x \notin F$. Since f is presemiclosed injection, $f(F)$ is semiclosed set in Y and $f(x) \notin f(F)$. Since Y is $s\beta$ -regular space and so there exist disjoint β -open sets U and V in Y such that $f(x) \in U$ and $f(F) \subset V$. By hypothesis, $f^{-1}(U)$ and $f^{-1}(V)$ are β -open sets in X with $x \in f^{-1}(U)$, $F \subset f^{-1}(V)$ and $f^{-1}(U) \cap f^{-1}(V) = \emptyset$. Hence X is $s\beta$ -regular. X is $s\beta$ -regular

THEOREM 5.6 *Every α - T_1 and $\alpha\beta$ -normal space is $\alpha\beta$ -regular*

Proof. : Let X be a α - T_1 -space and $\alpha\beta$ -normal space. Let F be any α -closed set in X and $x \in X - F$. As X is α - T_1 -space, $\{x\}$ is α -closed for all $x \in X$. Thus F and $\{x\}$ are two disjoint α -closed sets in X . Since X is $\alpha\beta$ -normal space, there exist disjoint β -open sets G and H in X such that $\{x\} \subset G$ and $F \subset H$ implies $x \in G$ and $F \subset H$. This shows X is $\alpha\beta$ -regular.

THEOREM 5.7 *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a α -irresolute, $\alpha\beta$ -closed surjection and X is $\alpha\beta$ - normal then so is Y .*

Proof. : Let A and B be any two disjoint α -closed sets in Y . Then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint α -closed sets of X . Since f is α -irresolute , $\alpha\beta$ - normal, there exist β - open sets U and V in X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$. By theorem [18], there exist β - open sets G and H of Y such that $A \subset G$ and $B \subset H$, $f^{-1}(G) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(H) \subset V$. Then $f^{-1}(G) \cap f^{-1}(H) = \emptyset$. Thus $G \cap H = \emptyset$. By theorem [18] Y is $\alpha\beta$ - normal.

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